

VITAMIN-C CONTENT OF SOME FRUITS AND VEGETABLES OF ASSAM

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The vitamin-C content of thirty-six samples of fruits and vegetables grown in Assam has been estimated. It is found that the vitamin-C content varies from province to province even for the same material, thus confirming earlier observations by other investigators.

A particular plant *Bryophyllum* shows increase in vitamin-C content when exposed to direct sunlight.

The determination of the vitamin-C content of Indian fruits and vegetables has been undertaken by various investigators (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 34; Rothenheim, Mahmud and Cowlage, *ibid.*, 1938, 15, 17; Sen-Gupta and Guha, *ibid.*, 1939, 16, 549; Mitra and Roy, *ibid.*, 1940, 17, 247). It has been found that vitamin-C content of the same material varies from place to place. Table I is illustrative of the variance of vitamin-C content of some of the substances grown in the different localities. Though in the other Indian provinces dietary surveys are carried out, yet no systematic investigation in this line has so far been undertaken in the province of Assam. An attempt therefore has been made to estimate the vitamin-C content of some common edibles (fruits and vegetables) of the province. The results of this investigation are shown in Table II.

In the present investigation with a particular plant *Bryophyllum* (Dupar-tenga), it is found that the amount of vitamin-C is greatest when exposed to direct sunlight. The same plant has been examined when it is covered with overhanging shrubs and then after the removal of the foliage. The results, shown in Table III, confirm the earlier observations of Giraud *et al.* (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1934, 117, 612) and Murray and Stratton (*J. Nutrition*, 1944, 28, 427) that vitamin-C content is greatest in plants exposed to full sunlight.

EXPERIMENTAL

The fruits and vegetables were samples found in and around the town of Gauhati and only fresh ones were taken, in many cases direct from the kitchen-gardens of the locality. In determining the vitamin-C content, the usual titrimetric method of Tillman as modified by Bessey and King (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 103, 687) was followed. The samples (10 g.) were ground to a thin paste in a glass mortar with acid-washed white sand and 25 c.c. of a solution containing 8% trichloroacetic acid and 2% meta-phosphoric acid. The mixture was centrifuged and the clear liquid decanted. The mortar was rinsed and the centrifuging repeated with consecutive 10 and 5 c.c. portions of the extracting liquid, and the combined extracts made up to 50 c.c. An aliquot of the extract was diluted with distilled water (from glass) and titrated from a micro-burette with a standard solution of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol, to a permanent faint pink end-point. A blank titration of an equivalent amount of extracting solution was also done. The analysis of each sample was completed in the same day following the recommendations of Mapson and Mawson (*Nature*, 1943, 151, 222).

TABLE I

Vitamin-C content of fruits and vegetables of different places

English name.	Scientific name.	Vitamin-C content in mg. per 100 g. of the substance			
		Assam	Bengal (Guha <i>et al.</i>)	Bihar (Mitra & Roy)	Other deter- minations
Bean	<i>Dolichos lab lab</i>	6.6	7	17.4—17.8	5—12.5*
Bottle gourd (leaves)	<i>Lageneria vulgaris</i>	8.5	5	33	..
Cabbage	<i>Brassica oleracea capitata</i>	27	14—20.8	..	25—75*
Chillies	<i>Capsicum indicum</i>	5.5	4 (Bombay) 45 (Malda) 10 (Patna)	..	10—20*
Indian plum	<i>Zizyphus jujuba</i>	12	..	22.3—30.5	..
Lemon	<i>Citrus medica</i>	17 [†]	36.1 [†]
Onion (green stalks)	<i>Allium sepa</i>	6	..	22.7	..
Orange	<i>Citrus auranticum</i>	36 [†]	18—30.6 [†]
Pumpkin (leaves)	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	9.2	11	38.7	..
Ridge gourd	<i>Luffa acutangulata</i>	18	..	15.8	..
Shaddock	<i>Citrus decumana</i>	7	26
Spinach	<i>Spinach oleracea</i>	6.4	6—14.9	41	..
Tomato	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum</i>	13	27.3
Wood-apple	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	7.5	18—86.7	4.7	..

TABLE II

Vernacular name.	English name.	Scientific name.	Values of vitamin-C content per 100 g. of substance
Bandha Kabi	Cabbage	<i>Brassica capitata</i>	27
Bilahibengena	Tomato	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum</i>	13
Urahi	Bean	<i>Dolichos lab-lab</i>	6.6
Jhilmil sak (leaves)	..	<i>Chinapodium album</i>	5
Sajina pat	Leaves of Horse radish	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	22.5
Sajina phul	Flowers of Horse radish	..	10
Lafa sak	Leaves of common mallow	<i>Malva verticillata</i>	4
Chuka sak	Leaves of Rumex	<i>Rumex vesicarius</i>	4
Babari sak	A kind of Basil	..	8
Mula sak	Leaves of Radish	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	5.6
Lai sak	..	<i>Brassica Rugosa</i>	4
Olkabi	..	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	10.6
Dhanis sak	Leaves of Coriander	<i>Coriandum sativum</i>	5.3
Lao-Ag	Tender leaves of white gourd	<i>Lageneria vulgaris</i>	8.5
Rangalao-Ag	Do of Pumpkin	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	9.2
Rangalao-phul	flowers of pumpkin	..	11
Farash	French-bean	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	8.8
Matar pat	Leaves of pea	<i>Pisicum arvensa</i>	7.3
Tengeahitenga	Oxalis	<i>Oxalis cornuculata</i>	4.5
Saf pat	Leaves of Anise	<i>Pimpinella anisum</i>	8.7

* These values are taken from Tables compiled by Hawk (Practical Physiological Chemistry, 11th edition).

† Per 100 c.c. of the pulp.

TABLE II (contd.)

Vernacular name.	English name.	Scientific name.	Values of vitamin-C content per 100 g. of substance
Dupar-tonga	Leaves of Bryophyllum	<i>Bryophyllum</i>	11.7
Paleng	Spinach	<i>Spinach oleracea</i>	6.4
Piyaz pat	Leaves of onion	<i>Allium sepa</i>	6
Jika	Ridge-gourd	<i>Luffa acutangulata</i>	16
Amlakhi	Emblic myrobalan	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	7.2
Outenga	..	<i>Dillenia indica</i>	10.8 (unripe Sept. 3.2 (ripe Dec.))
Kardai (ripe)	Carambola	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i>	2.3
Jalpai	Olive	<i>Elaeocarpus serratus</i>	4
Sumtheratenga	Orange	<i>Citrus auranticum</i>	43 per 100 c.c. (Oct.) 36 " (Jan.)
Nemutenga (ripe)	Lemon	<i>Citrus medica</i>	17 per 100 c.c.
Bel (ripe)	Wood-apple	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	7.5
Amara (ripe)	Hog plum	<i>Spondius mangijera</i>	4.3
Bagari	Indian plum	<i>Zizyphus jujuba</i>	12
Rabab Tenga (ripe)	Shaddock	<i>Citrus decumana</i>	7
Amita (unripe)	Papaya	<i>Carica Papaya</i>	14
Jalakia	Green chillies	<i>Capsicum indicus</i>	5.5

TABLE III

Date of estimation.	Condition of the plant. (<i>Bryophyllum</i>)	Vitamin-C content in mg. per 100 g. of leaves.
21.10.45	Covered with overhangings	4.3
3.1.46	After removal of overhangings on 22.10.45	11.7

DISCUSSION

From Tables I and II, it is seen that vitamin-C content of the same substances grown in the three different Indian provinces (Bengal, Bihar and Assam) varies. The vitamin-C content of substances growing in Bihar records a maximum with least values for Assam. An exception is seen in the cases of orange juice and cabbage. This may be explained by the fact that the oranges and cabbages were fresh from the gardens in this determination while in a city like Calcutta they might not have been available in such a fresh condition. It is found that with maturity the vitamin-C content gradually decreases in the case of *Dillenia Indica* thus confirming the view of Ghosh and Guha (*loc. cit.*). It may possibly be due to this reason that we notice rather too low values for carambola, lemon, shaddock and hog plum, which were very ripe at the time of investigation.

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